

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Article

Pharmacognostical Review on Herbal Drugs Used in Treatment of Skin Disorders

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ARTICLE INFO

Published: 17 Nov 2025

Keywords:

Butea

monosperma, Syzygium
cumini, Sinensis Flowers

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.17628077

ABSTRACT

The skin, being the largest organ of the human body, serves as a protective barrier, regulates temperature, and maintains overall homeostasis, yet it is frequently affected by a range of disorders such as acne, pimples, scars, itchiness, aging, fungal infections, pigmentation disorders, inflammatory or allergic conditions, and boils. These problems often arise due to oxidative stress, microbial invasion, dryness, and impaired skin barrier function. Moisturizers play a vital role in managing these issues by hydrating the epidermis, restoring barrier integrity, balancing surface pH, and reducing discomfort. With increasing demand for safe, natural, and multifunctional products, herbal-based formulations are gaining prominence in skincare. Nowadays, herbal skincare products are becoming more popular because they are safe, natural, and effective. Medicinal plants like *Butea monosperma* (Palash), *Syzygium cumini* (Jamun), and *Hibiscus rosa-sinensis* (China rose) are known for their beneficial effects on the skin. *Butea monosperma* has antimicrobial and healing properties, *Syzygium cumini* works as a strong antioxidant, and *Hibiscus rosa-sinensis* helps in soothing and rejuvenating the skin. This review discusses the importance of these herbal ingredients in improving skin health and managing common skin problems. Herbal multipurpose creams made from such plants can serve as safe and effective alternatives to chemical-based skincare products.

INTRODUCTION

The skin, being the largest organ of the human body, serves as a physical and immunological barrier, regulates body temperature, and maintains internal homeostasis. Despite its protective

functions, it is frequently affected by various disorders such as acne, scars, pigmentation anomalies, aging, fungal infections, and allergic or inflammatory conditions. These problems are often caused by factors including oxidative stress, microbial infections, transepidermal water loss, and impaired skin barrier integrity [1,2].

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Topical creams are commonly used in dermatology to address these conditions. Among these, herbal multipurpose creams are gaining increasing popularity due to their natural origin, multifunctional efficacy, and minimal side effects. Such formulations often utilize plant-based bioactive compounds—like flavonoids, tannins, alkaloids, and saponins—which exert antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, moisturizing, and wound-healing effects through multiple pharmacological pathways [32–8-33].

This review highlights the potential of a polyherbal topical formulation comprising *Butea monosperma* (Palash), *Syzygium cumini* (Jamun), and *Hibiscus rosa-sinensis* (China rose). *Butea monosperma* is known for its antimicrobial, antioxidant, and wound-healing properties [9–10]. *Syzygium cumini* exhibits strong antioxidant activity and supports pigmentation control and skin regeneration [9–3-11]. *Hibiscus rosa-sinensis* contributes to skin hydration, brightening, and anti-aging effects, due to its rich content of anthocyanins, flavonoids, and vitamin C [12–4].

This is a review on skin and skin disorders and herbal ingredients that contain properties for skin healing or various skin problems that they treat. Herbal ingredients are *Butea monosperma* (Palash), *Syzygium cumini* (Jamun), and *Hibiscus rosa-sinensis* (China rose). These are herbal ingredients or highlighted skin disorders such as acne, pimples, scars, itchiness, aging, fungal infections, pigmentation disorders, inflammatory or allergic conditions, and boils.

Structurally, human skin consists of three main layers:

Epidermis – The **epidermis** is the **outermost layer of the skin**, composed primarily of keratinized stratified squamous epithelium. It serves as the body's first line of defense against

environmental insults, such as microbial invasion, chemical exposure, dehydration, and ultraviolet (UV) radiation.[6]

Dermis – The **dermis** is the **middle layer of the skin**, located beneath the epidermis and above the subcutaneous tissue (hypodermis). It is composed mainly of **connective tissue** (collagen and elastin fibers) and provides mechanical strength, elasticity, and support to the skin.[34]

Hypodermis - (subcutaneous tissue) – The **hypodermis** is the **deepest layer of the skin**, lying beneath the dermis. It is not technically part of the skin but is closely associated with it. The hypodermis is primarily composed of **loose connective tissue** and **adipose tissue**, which act as insulation, energy storage, and cushioning against external forces.[8]

Fig.No.1 Three layers of Skin

Common Skin Disorders

- Acne
- Pimples
- Fade scars
- Itchiness
- Skin Aging

- Fungal Infections
- Pigmentation Disorders
- Inflammatory / Allergic conditions
- Boils

Common Skin Disorders

ACNE:

Acne, also known as acne vulgaris, is a long-term skin condition that occurs when dead skin cells and oil from the skin clog hair follicles. Typical features of the condition include blackheads or whiteheads, pimples, oily skin, and possible scarring. It primarily affects skin with a relatively high number of oil glands, including the face, upper part of the chest, and back. The resulting appearance can lead to lack of confidence, anxiety, reduced self-esteem, and, in extreme cases, depression or thoughts of suicide.

Susceptibility to acne is primarily genetic in 80% of cases. The roles of diet and cigarette smoking in the condition are unclear, and neither cleanliness nor exposure to sunlight are associated with acne. In both sexes, hormones called androgens appear to be part of the underlying mechanism, by causing increased production of sebum. Another common factor is the excessive growth of the bacterium *Cutibacterium acnes*, which is present on the skin.[16,24]

Fig.No.5 Acne

Pimple

Acne vulgaris is a common cutaneous inflammatory disorder of the pilosebaceous unit, which runs a chronic course. The condition commonly manifests with papules, pustules, or nodules primarily on the face, although it can also affect the upper arms, trunk, and back. The pathogenesis of acne vulgaris involves the interaction of multiple factors that ultimately lead to the formation of its primary lesion, which is known as “comedo” (see Image. Acne Vulgaris). Although acne vulgaris is commonly observed among adolescents, it is not restricted to this age group and can affect individuals of various ages. The severity of this condition can vary, ranging from a mild presentation with only a few comedones to more severe forms characterized by disfiguring inflammatory manifestations, which can lead to hyperpigmentation, scarring, and adverse psychological effects.[17,36,19]

Fade Scars

A scar (or scar tissue) is an area of fibrous tissue that replaces normal skin after an injury. Scars result from the biological process of wound repair in the skin, as well as in other organs, and tissues of the body. Thus, scarring is a natural part of the

healing process. With the exception of very minor lesions, every wound (e.g., after accident, disease, or surgery) results in some degree of scarring. An exception to this are animals with complete regeneration, which regrow tissue without scar formation.

Scar tissue is composed of the same protein (collagen) as the tissue that it replaces, but the fiber composition of the protein is different; instead of a random basketweave formation of the collagen fibers found in normal tissue, in fibrosis the collagen cross-links and forms a pronounced alignment in a single direction. This collagen scar tissue alignment is usually of inferior functional quality to the normal collagen randomised alignment. For example, scars in the skin are less resistant to ultraviolet radiation, and sweat glands and hair follicles do not grow back within scar tissues. A myocardial infarction, commonly known as a heart attack, causes scar formation in the heart muscle, which leads to loss of muscular power and possibly heart failure. However, there are some tissues (e.g. bone) that can heal without any structural or functional deterioration.[37,38,48,39]

Fig.No.6 Fade Scars

Itchiness

Itch is a topic to which everyone can relate. The physiological roles of itch are increasingly understood and appreciated. The pathophysiological consequences of itch impact quality of life as much as pain. These dynamics have led to increasingly deep dives into the mechanisms that underlie and contribute to the sensation of itch. When the prior review on the physiology of itching was published in this journal in 1941, itch was a black box of interest to a small number of neuroscientists and dermatologists. Itch is now appreciated as a complex and colorful Rubik's cube. Acute and chronic itch are being carefully scratched apart and reassembled by puzzle solvers across the biomedical spectrum. New mediators are being identified. Mechanisms blur boundaries of the circuitry that blend neuroscience and immunology. Measures involve psychophysics and behavioral psychology. The efforts associated with these approaches are positively impacting the care of itchy patients. There is now the potential to markedly alleviate chronic itch, a condition that does not end life, but often ruins it. We review the itch field and provide a current understanding of the pathophysiology of itch. Itch is a disease, not only a symptom of disease.[32,21]

Fig.No.7 Itchiness

Skin Aging

Ageing is a natural phenomenon which is a fold, ridge and crease in the skin that occurs due to loss of body mass, poor hydration, disintegration of dermis and epidermis junction. The Skin ageing process involves many changes that occur due to the combination of both endogenous factors (gene mutation, cellular metabolism, and hormonal factor) and exogenous factors (U.V, pollutants, chemical, and toxins). In 1950, the number of older people were found to be almost 205 million across the globe. But this number almost got 4 times by the year 2012 and the number of older persons increased to a massive amount of 810 million. The ageing of the skin occurs due to various mechanisms like glycation, free radical, cell cycle, and cellular and molecular mechanism of skin.[22,23,37]

Fig.No.8 Skin Aging

Fungal Infection

Fungal infections are common skin, hair, and nail disorders caused by a variety of fungi, including dermatophytes, yeasts (e.g., *Candida* species), and molds, collectively known as mycoses. They are classified based on the depth of tissue involvement: superficial mycoses affect only the outermost layers of skin and hair, cutaneous mycoses involve keratinized tissues such as the skin, hair, and nails, subcutaneous mycoses penetrate deeper layers of the dermis and

subcutaneous tissue, and systemic fungal infections can affect internal organs, especially in immunocompromised individuals [24,39,40].

Fig.No.9 Fungal Infection

Pigmentation Disorders

Pigmentation Of the skin normally varies according to racial origin (see Fitzpatrick phototypes) and the amount of sun exposure. Pigmentation disorders are often more troublesome in skin of colour.

The melanocytes (pigment cells) are located at the base of the epidermis and produce the protein melanin. Melanin is carried by keratinocytes to the skin surface. The melanocytes of dark-skinned people produce more melanin than those of people with light skin. More melanin is produced when

the skin is injured, for example following exposure to ultraviolet radiation. The melanisation process in dark skin is protective against sun damage, but melanisation in white skin (for example after sunburn) is much less protective.

Hormonal effects of oestrogen during pregnancy or due to medication can cause pigmentation of nipples, vulva and abdomen (linea nigra).

Some skin diseases and conditions result in generalised or localised hyperpigmentation (increased skin colour, hypermelanosis), hypopigmentation (reduced skin colour,

hypomelanosis), or depigmentation (absent skin colour, leukoderma).

A Wood lamp may be used to assess pigmentation during the examination of the skin, as pigmentary changes are often easier to identify while exposing the affected skin to longwavelength ultraviolet rays .[41,25]

Fig.No.10 Pigmentation Disorder

Allergic Condition

An allergy is a specific type of exaggerated immune response where the body mistakenly identifies an ordinarily harmless substance (allergens, like pollen, pet dander, or certain foods) as a threat and launches a defense against it.

Allergic diseases are the conditions that arise as a result of allergic reactions, such as hay fever, allergic conjunctivitis, allergic asthma, atopic dermatitis, food allergies, and anaphylaxis. Symptoms of the above diseases may include red eyes, an itchy rash, sneezing, coughing, a runny nose, shortness of breath, or swelling. Note that food intolerances and food poisoning are separate conditions.

Common allergens include pollen and certain foods. Metals and other substances may also cause such problems. Food, insect stings, and medications are common causes of severe reactions. Their development is due to both genetic

and environmental factors. The underlying mechanism involves immunoglobulin E antibodies (IgE), part of the body's immune system, binding to an allergen and then to a receptor on mast cells or basophils where it triggers the release of inflammatory chemicals such as histamine. Diagnosis is typically based on a person's medical history. Further testing of the skin or blood may be useful in certain cases. Positive tests, however, may not necessarily mean there is a significant allergy to the substance in question. [26,27,41,49,50]

Boils

A boil (furuncle) is a pus-filled bump in the skin that is caused by a bacterial infection. It is a bit like a very big yellow pimple, but it's deeper in the skin and hurts a lot more.

Boils develop when a hair follicle and the surrounding tissue become infected. Hair follicles consist of one hair, the root of the hair, a sebaceous gland and a small muscle that can pull the hair up, making it stand on end. Hair follicle inflammations are sometimes also referred to as "deep folliculitis" or "perifolliculitis." [44,45,46,47]

The infection causes the skin tissue inside the boil to die, creating a pus-filled hollow space (an abscess). Skin abscesses can develop from boils, but also from other things like infected insect bites or injections with dirty needles. If several boils merge into a larger bump, it's called a carbuncle.

Sometimes boils go away again on their own, without causing any problems. But it's often a good idea to get medical treatment. This can help make boils go away quicker, relieve the pain and prevent complications. [42,43,28,29,30,7,31]

Fig.No.11 Boils

Herbal Ingredients: -

Butea monosperma (Palash) – Leaves

Fig.No. Butea Monosperma Leaves

Flavonoids

Butin: A flavonoid compound known for its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial properties. It helps protect the skin from free radicals, thereby reducing signs of aging.

Isobutrin: Another flavonoid that exhibits antioxidant activity and helps in protecting the skin from oxidative damage.

Butein: Known for its anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial effects, it can promote skin healing and reduce irritation.

Tannins

Gallic acid: A polyphenol that has antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory properties. It is often used to treat skin conditions like acne, eczema, and wounds.

Ellagic acid: Known for its anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties, which can promote skin rejuvenation and help with sun damage.

Alkaloids

Palasine: An alkaloid found in Butea monosperma that is believed to contribute to the plant's antimicrobial properties. It may help reduce infections and inflammations in the skin.

Cytisine: Though more known for its role in other therapeutic areas, it may also play a part in reducing skin inflammation.

Saponins

Saponins are known to have mild antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory effects. They can help in treating minor skin infections and may assist in improving skin texture.

Glycoside

Certain glycosides in Butea monosperma, such as butrin, may support tissue regeneration and healing, which is beneficial for wound care.

The flowers of Butea monosperma contain essential oils with antimicrobial properties, which may help in treating conditions like acne, fungal infections, and general skin irritation.

Uses:

Acne treatment: Due to its anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial properties, Butea monosperma can be used in creams or oils to treat acne and prevent future breakouts.

Anti-aging products: The antioxidants can be incorporated into skin care products aimed at reducing wrinkles, fine lines, and other signs of aging.

Wound Healing: Used in ointments for cuts, burns, and skin irritation to speed up the healing process.

Skin tone improvement: The plant's compounds can help to lighten dark spots and improve overall skin tone by reducing oxidative damage.[35,10,11,12,13]

Kingdom Of Butea Monosperma

Table No.1

Taxonomy	Classification
Kingdom	Plantae
Clade	Tracheophytes
Clade	Angiosperm
Clade	Eudicots
Clade	Rosids
Order	Fabales
Family	Fabaceae
Sub-family	Faboideae
Genus	Butea
Species	B.monosperma

Hibiscus rosa-sinensis:

Fig.No.3 Hibiscus Rosa Sinensi

Constituents:

Anthocyanins: These are the primary pigments in the flowers, responsible for their red, pink, or purple colors.

Flavonoids: A class of antioxidants that includes compounds like quercetin, kaempferol, and myricetin.

Organic Acids: Hibiscus is rich in organic acids, such as:

- Citric acid
- Hibiscus acid (HA)
- Malic acid
- Ascorbic acid (Vitamin C)
- Hydroxycitric acid (HCA)
- **Terpenoids and Alkaloids:** These are other classes of bioactive compounds found in the flowers.
- **Tannins:** A group of phenolic compounds present in hibiscus.
- **Proteins and Amino Acids:** The flowers also contain proteins and free amino acids, such as aspartic acid and asparagine.
- **Vitamins and Minerals:** Hibiscus flowers contain some B vitamins (like thiamine and riboflavin) and minerals such as iron, calcium, and phosphorus.

Uses:

Anti-aging

The combination of antioxidants like anthocyanins, flavonoids, and Vitamin C helps protect the skin from free radical damage, which accelerates aging. Regular use of hibiscus extracts or oils may help reduce wrinkles, fine lines, and sagging skin.

Brightening and Even Skin Tone

Hibiscus is known for its ability to brighten the skin due to its high vitamin C content. Vitamin C

helps inhibit melanin production, thus reducing hyperpigmentation and dark spots, resulting in a more even and radiant skin tone.

Acne Treatment

The antimicrobial properties of hibiscus, particularly due to hibiscine and flavonoids, make it effective for preventing and treating acne. It helps to control excess oil, soothe inflammation, and prevent bacterial infections that can lead to acne breakouts.

Moisturizing and Hydrating

Polysaccharides in hibiscus petals provide excellent hydration by forming a moisture-retaining barrier on the skin, making it an ideal ingredient for dry or sensitive skin. Regular use can help keep the skin soft, smooth, and plump.

Soothing and Calming

Hibiscus has anti-inflammatory effects due to its flavonoid and tannin content. It helps soothe and calm irritated skin, reducing redness and inflammation from conditions like eczema, psoriasis, or sunburn.

Wound Healing

Hibiscus's antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties help speed up the healing of minor cuts, burns, and wounds, promoting faster tissue regeneration and minimizing scarring.

Anti-pigmentation

Due to its tannin and Vitamin C content, hibiscus is often used in skin care products that target pigmentation issues, including sun spots, age spots, and melasma. It helps lighten

hyperpigmented areas and even out skin tone.[14,5,6]

Kingdom Of Hibiscus Rosa Senensis

Table No.2

Taxonomy	Classification
Kingdom	Plantae
Clade	Tracheophytes
Clade	Angiosperm
Clade	Eudicots
Clade	Rosids
Order	Malvales
Family	Malvaceae
Sub-family	Malvoideae
Genus	Hibisceae
Species	<i>Hibiscus L.</i>

Jamun Seeds –

Chemical Constituents:

1.Flavonoids

Quercetin: A potent antioxidant with anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and anti-aging properties. It helps in protecting the skin from oxidative stress, reducing skin aging, and calming inflammatory skin conditions like acne or eczema.

Kaempferol: Known for its antioxidant effects, kaempferol also has anti-inflammatory and skin-healing properties. It can support skin barrier repair and help reduce oxidative damage caused by UV rays.

Tannins

Ellagic acid: A polyphenol that provides strong antioxidant and anti-inflammatory benefits. It helps protect the skin from UV-induced damage, reduces pigmentation, and promotes overall skin health.

Gallic acid: Another key tannin compound in Jamun seeds with antioxidant and antimicrobial effects, which is beneficial for treating acne and minor skin infections.

Anthocyanins

Cyanidin-3-glucoside: This is the primary anthocyanin in Jamun seeds, responsible for their deep purple color. It has potent antioxidant properties that can help prevent premature aging of the skin and protect against oxidative stress.

Alkaloids

Jambosine: This compound, found in Jamun seeds, has anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial effects that can be useful in preventing acne, skin infections, and irritation.

Syzyginine: Another alkaloid that may contribute to the anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial properties of Jamun seeds, helping to alleviate conditions like acne and other skin inflammations.

Flavonoid Glycosides

Myricetin: Known for its antioxidant properties, myricetin helps in reducing skin damage caused by free radicals and environmental pollutants. It can also reduce the appearance of wrinkles and improve skin tone.

Saponins

Saponins in Jamun seeds may contribute to its antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory properties.

They can help cleanse the skin, prevent acne, and soothe irritation.

Polyphenolic Compounds

Ellagitannins: These compounds exhibit both antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects. They help protect the skin from oxidative stress, improve collagen synthesis, and promote wound healing.

Uses

Anti-aging Properties

The antioxidants like quercetin, kaempferol, and cyanidin help reduce the formation of free radicals, preventing premature aging signs such as wrinkles, fine lines, and age spots. Regular use of Jamun seed extracts may enhance skin elasticity and firmness.

Anti-inflammatory

Tannins, alkaloids, and flavonoids (such as quercetin and kaempferol) have strong anti-inflammatory properties, making Jamun seeds useful for treating inflammatory skin conditions like acne, eczema, and psoriasis. They help calm the skin and reduce redness, swelling, and irritation.

Antioxidant Protection

The anthocyanins, flavonoids, and polyphenols in Jamun seeds act as potent antioxidants, neutralizing free radicals and protecting the skin from oxidative stress, which is a major factor in premature aging and skin damage.

Acne Treatment

Antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory properties of Jamun seeds help treat acne by reducing inflammation, preventing infection, and regulating

oil production. They may help cleanse the skin and prevent future breakouts.

Pigmentation Reduction

Ellagic acid and gallic acid help reduce hyperpigmentation by inhibiting melanin production. This can help lighten dark spots, acne scars, and even out skin tone.

Wound Healing and Skin Repair

The flavonoid glycosides and tannins in Jamun seeds promote faster wound healing and tissue regeneration. The compounds stimulate collagen production and accelerate skin repair processes, which is useful for treating cuts, burns, and other skin injuries.

Antimicrobial Effects

The alkaloids (such as jambosine) and saponins in Jamun seeds have antimicrobial properties that can help prevent and treat skin infections caused by bacteria, fungi, or viruses. These compounds help prevent acne and other skin infections caused by microbial growth.[14,18,15,20,21]

Kingdom Of Jamun Seeds

Table No.3

Taxonomy	Classification
Kingdom	Plantae
Clade	Tracheophytes
Clade	Angiosperm
Clade	Eudicots
Clade	Rosids
Order	Myrtales
Family	Myrtaceae
Genus	Syzygium
Species	<i>S. cumini</i>

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HOW TO CITE: Kavita Sharma*, Pratik Jejurkar, Gaurav Zalte, Sushant Kadam, Pharmacognostical Review on Herbal Drugs Used in Treatment of Skin Disorders, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 11, 2481-2494 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17628077>

